

Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment as Predictors of Organizational Commitment

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Abstract

Organizational commitment is a vital factor in determining the turnover intention of employees in the workplace. This study aimed to examine the relationship and predictive ability of Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment to Organizational Commitment. With the use of purposive sampling, a total of 250 respondents were gathered from call center agencies and former call center agents within Metro Manila. Results of the study suggests that Agreeableness and Organizational Commitment is significant and has weak positive correlation ($r = .22$; $p < .01$); Attachment Style and Organizational Commitment has no significance; Relationship Commitment and Organizational Commitment bears the greatest positive correlation and is significant ($r = .51$, $p < .001$). In connection, using Multiple Linear Regression showed that, as a whole, Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment is significant in predicting Organizational Commitment. Implication of the study suggest that an individual's commitment to personal relationships can be a predictor of an individual's commitment to an organization and may help in screening applicants preventing unwanted turnovers.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational Commitment has been considered as a common predictor of many variables especially involving in any workplace setting. Some of these that organizational commitment predicts are: the effectiveness of teams in a workplace and the job satisfaction involved in the employees (Lee, 2003); the stress and the affected performance of the employee (Siu, 2003); and most importantly, turnover intentions and actual turnovers of employees (Steenbergen and Ellemers, 2009). Although, organizational commitment may be one of the most accurate predictors of some of the variables mentioned above, however, there is a lack in what predicts organizational commitment. There are some that involves the culture of an organization (Lok et al, 2005), also the age, tenure, and resources of control of an employee (Brimeyer et al, 2010), and even the mere appointment of an employee to a higher position (Bland et al, 2006). Studies in the Philippines are limited regarding organizational commitment; and it was also done with the aforementioned variables such as job satisfaction, stress, and also with leadership (Chavez, 2012), both these studies are predicted by organizational commitment but it does not predict organizational commitment.

In abroad, across the entire industry, call centers replace 26 percent of their front-line

agents annually, according to Response Design Corporation in 2009. This means that at a company with 1,000, for instance, managers should expect 260 telemarketers to leave voluntarily or involuntarily by the end of the year. Actual turnover rates vary by sector within the industry and the classification of an employee may affect his expected attrition rate. For example, turnover for part-time employees hovers around 33 percent annually (Huebsch, 2011). In the Philippines, there is a prevalence in the turnover rate of employees in call center agencies. In an article by GMA News Online published on March 20, 2008, "Republic of the Philippines' call centers reel from world's highest turnover." Mentioned in the article is that: Turnover rate in the country's call centers has gotten so worse that it has hit 60 to 80 percent, according to the Call Center Association of the Philippines (CCAP). This has given the Philippines the world's highest turnover rate for call centers worldwide. Globally, it is an accepted norm in the industry to have a 30 to 40 per cent turnover. Both Australia and India call centers have turnover rates of only six to 10 percent. Top government officials are alarmed that an emerging industry that has generated around 2 billion US dollars in annual revenues is reeling from a worsening turnover crisis (Pena, 2008).

In abroad, the current trend in addressing employee turnover according to Missouri Business are: hiring the right people and continue developing their careers, company must be very employee oriented, develop an overall strategic compensation package (Mushbrush, 2014). In addition, A 2001 CallCenterCareer.com survey found that recognition for a job well done motivates call center employees almost as much as an increase in pay. Managers should consider fun ways to recognize top employees, such as a day at a spa or a gaming console, for the best performer on a certain day. The company should also consider a reward for the employee that shows the most improvement. Paul Weald, director at RXPerience Limited, suggests that managers spend several hours each month developing each employee's skill set by sitting in on calls and remotely monitoring random calls. The hiring manager should also look for good fits for a call center job. For instance, students offer call centers a cheap and plentiful source of labor, but the ideal candidate likely wants to use a call center job to start a career in sales (Huebsch, 2011). In the Philippines, regarding the current trend in addressing employee turnover, in an article by Philippine Daily Inquirer published on May 22, 2011, "Work-life programs and organizational commitment." Mentioned in the article is that: It was found that employees were generally satisfied with their organization's work-life programs as evidenced in their positive perception of their respective company's retirement plan, home plan, healthcare and insurance plan. Furthermore, Results support the positive relationship of work-life policies and organizational commitment. It also showed that employees' attitude on work-life programs and organizational commitment responds to three levels of need: (1) security, (2) socialization or belongingness and, (3) professional and personal growth. Consequently, satisfaction with work-life initiatives lessens the tendency of employees to leave the organization (Ramos, 2004). The implication of both trends create the need for organizational commitment to be established in an organization to address turnover prevention. Having organizationally committed employees creates the notion, "We work to live not live to work."

With all these scenarios, the researcher is keenly interested in understanding the predictors of organizational commitment in the grounds of Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment. It is stated that relationships are affected by a personality variable, and even attachment style in relation to organizational commitment, Tashiro and Frazier (2003). Furthermore, this study could provide a useful additive to the literature of organizational commitment in the Philippines, since there are few studies done locally, and would be beneficial to any academic institutions in addressing organizational problems and issues.

This study aims to determine the predictive ability of agreeableness, attachment style, and relationship commitment to organizational commitment in a call center agency in the Philippines. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the degree of agreeableness, attachment style, relationship commitment, and organizational commitment of the respondents?
2. Is there a significant relationship between agreeableness and organizational commitment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between attachment style and organizational commitment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between relationship commitment and organizational commitment?
5. Is the predictive model agreeableness, attachment style, and relationship commitment predict organizational commitment of the respondents?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Agreeableness

In a study by K. Kumar and A. Bakhshi (2010) regarding organizational commitment on the Five Factor Model of Personality, their results indicated that Openness to experience negatively predicted continuance and normative commitment. Conscientiousness positively predicted affective and continuance commitment. Extraversion emerged as the most consistent predictor, significantly relating (positively) to all three forms of organizational commitment. Normative commitment was found to be positively predicted by agreeableness. Neuroticism was found to have negative (non-significant) relationship with affective commitment, positive relationship with continuance commitment and positive (non-significant) relationship with normative commitment.

In a similar study done by T. Tashiro and P. Frazier (2003) regarding one of the factors of the Five Factor Model of Personality: Agreeableness and its significance to relationships, their results have found that correlates of self-reported growth included causal attributions to environmental factors and the personality factor of Agreeableness. Women reported more growth than did men. Factors related to higher levels of distress included causal attributions to the ex-partner and to environmental factors surrounding the previous relationship.

In a study by Liao, Joshi, and Chuang (2004); in their study, the results revealed that

dissimilarities in ethnicity, Agreeableness, and Openness to Experience were significantly related to organizational deviance; dissimilarities in gender, Conscientiousness, and Extraversion were significantly related to interpersonal deviance. In addition, ethnic dissimilarity negatively predicted POS and organizational commitment, age dissimilarity positively predicted perceived coworker support, Extraversion dissimilarity positively predicted coworker satisfaction, Agreeableness dissimilarity negatively predicted POS, and Openness to Experience dissimilarity negatively predicted POS, organizational commitment, perceived coworker support, and coworker satisfaction.

Attachment Style

In a study done by Boatwright et al. (2010) regarding attachment style and work related variables such as work preferences and leadership behaviors, their findings revealed that workers with preoccupied adult attachment styles expressed stronger preferences for relational leadership behaviors than workers with either dismissive adult attachment styles or fearful attachment styles. John Bowlby and Mary Ainsworth founded modern attachment theory on studies of children and their caregivers. Children and caregivers remained the primary focus of attachment theory for many years. Then, in the late 1980s, Cindy Hazan and Phillip Shaver applied attachment theory to adult romantic relationships. Hazan and Shaver noticed that interactions between adult romantic partners shared similarities to interactions between children and caregivers. For example, romantic partners desire to be close to one another. Romantic partners feel comforted when their partners are present and anxious or lonely when their partners are absent. Romantic relationships serve as a secure base that help partners face the surprises, opportunities, and challenges life presents. Similarities such as these led Hazan and Shaver to extend attachment theory to adult romantic relationships (Hazan C. and Shaver P.R., 1987).

Relationship Commitment

In a study done by De Goede et al. (2011) regarding relationship commitment, their Multivariate growth curves showed that higher base levels of commitment and a stronger positive development of commitment to parents and friends were associated with higher levels of later commitment to romantic partners. The effects were equally strong in early-to-middle adolescence and middle-to-late adolescence. Also, commitment to parents and commitment to friends were associated equally strong to romantic relationship commitment. No gender differences were found regarding these linkages. Overall, this study shows the importance of parents and friends for boys and girls regarding committed romantic relationships. The results support the idea of one stable and general working model used in different types of relationships. Another study done by Oner (2000) regarding relationship commitment and its Future Time Orientation, their results found that although a general FTO was adaptive in terms of romantic relationships, a high concern for future commitment to a romantic relationship had a negative effect on reported relationship satisfaction.

In a similar study done by Schindler et al. (2010) regarding relationship commitment, their results have found that whether general attachment to romantic partners was predictive of single

individuals' progressing from not dating to dating and from not dating or casual dating to a committed and exclusive relationship when simultaneously considering desire for starting a committed relationship, prior dating involvement, and self-perceived physical attractiveness. Attachment avoidance, but not anxiety, was predictive of not entering into committed dating relationships even with rival predictors included. The transition from not dating to casual or committed dating was mainly predicted by prior dating success with some support for a potential additional role of the desire to form a committed relationship.

Organizational Commitment

In the last 10 years, several studies done by Lee, 2003; Trimble, 2006; Zhao et al., 2007; have been explored dealing with Organizational Commitment. Lee (2003) had findings that indicates group cohesiveness strengthened the positive relationship between trust and organizational commitment, while it did not affect the relationship between job-satisfaction and organizational commitment. Similarly, Trimble (2006) had findings that sheds light on an issue from organizational psychology: affective organizational commitment plays a mediating role between job satisfaction and turnover intention, rather than job satisfaction mediating affective organizational commitment and turnover intention. Also a study done by Wayne et al. (2007) had results indicated that affect mediates the effect of breach on attitude and individual effectiveness. All studies shows the role of Organizational Commitment with regards to job satisfaction, group cohesiveness, and individual effectiveness.

In a study done by Van-Dijk and Kirk-Brown (2003) regarding Organizational Commitment and its relation to job embeddedness and intention of leaving an organization, the findings of the study did not demonstrate a significant relationship between job embeddedness and intention to leave, although a significant relationship was found between organizational commitment and intention to leave. The results did not demonstrate a consistent pattern for the influence of gender or family responsibility. The results of the present study do however suggest that further development and refinement of the meaning and measurement of the job embeddedness construct will eventually result in a worthwhile contribution to the research literature. In a similar study, by Steenbergen and Ellemers (2009) regarding the relation of organizational commitment and work performance and behavior, Two studies (N1 = 16,389; N2 = 482) supported the distinction between these forms of work commitment, in addition to affective and continuance organizational commitment. Corroborating our predictions, organizational commitment predicted organizational turnover intentions and actual turnover, whereas the three forms of work commitment substantially improved the prediction of self-reported (Study 1) and objective (Study 2) measures of internal mobility and job performance over time.

In a study by Siu (2003) regarding Organizational commitment and job stress and work values, Chinese work values were found to be significant moderators of the stress–performance relationship in both samples. However, those values only safeguarded performance when work stress was low or moderately high. When work stress was very high, employees with high levels

of Chinese work values reported lower job performance. Organizational commitment, in contrast, protected employees from the negative effects of stressors and moderated the stress–performance relationship in a positive direction, but for the first sample only. The implications of the study are that it is essential to nourish work values among employees and cultivate employees’ commitment to their organizations. However, in very high stress situations, it is more appropriate to alter the work environment to reduce stressors at work, in order to enhance job performance. Similarly, a study done by Fernet et al. (2012) regarding organizational commitment in work exhaustion and motivation, their findings advance the understanding of why work motivation acts on employee functioning and how it can play an active role in both the motivational and energetic processes of the job demands-resources model.

In the last ten years, studies done by Freund & Drach-Zahavy (2007); Chang and Choi (2007); regarding the relation of organizational commitment and organizational politics; Freund & Drach-Zahavy (2007), in the findings of their study several interesting conclusions arise: first, team members seem convinced of the importance of teamwork and its contribution to their work, yet teamwork prevalence is still low. Second, the professional groups differ in their perception of teamwork goals and the way to attain them. The paraprofessionals are especially salient in that respect. Third, although clinic members see their role as structured more bureaucratically, the combination of mechanistic and organic job structuring led to teamwork effectiveness. Fourth, although team members are committed primarily to their profession and not to the organization, it is self-evident that organizational commitment should lead to team effectiveness. Finally, affective commitment exerted a much more significant influence on team effectiveness than did role structuring variables.

In a study by Brimeyer et al. (2010) regarding age, tenure, and resources for control in relation to organizational commitment, their findings suggest that the relationship between organizational commitment and predictors is affected by worker career stage. Most significantly, the commitment for older and more experienced workers increases with high levels of autonomy, while the opposite is true for younger and less experienced workers. When workers experience greater control at the point of production, they express greater organizational commitment. Although empowering for older and experienced workers, having freedom at work can be threatening or destabilizing for the younger workers, who may prefer more guidance.

In a study done by Bland et al. (2006) regarding the impact of appointment on productivity and organizational commitment, their findings indicate that whether one looks at all full-time faculty or just at newly hired full-time faculty in Research and Doctoral institutions, compared to their non-tenure colleagues, faculty on tenure appointments are significantly more productive in research, more productive in education, more committed to their positions, and work about four more hours each week (the equivalent of one additional month of work each year).

SYNTHESIS

The different studies conducted on Organizational Commitment have shown us the different variables that are correlated with Organizational Commitment. We have seen that organizational commitment plays a mediating role on job-satisfaction and organizational commitment predicted turnover intentions and actual turnovers. We have also found that the fairness in the change process interact with the effects of work unit changes on organizational commitment. In addition, we found that psychological contract breach decreases organizational commitment. Organizational commitment also has shown that it protected employees from the negative effects of stressors and moderated the stress–performance relationship in a positive direction. It was also mentioned that ethnic dissimilarity negatively predicted organizational commitment. People in their 40s in the workplace does not perceive organizational politics and organizational commitment to be related, but those who are younger moderately believed the two to be related. And it was also shown that organizational culture and subculture has a strong relationship with organizational commitment. Organizational commitment also has a strong influence on team effectiveness. It was also shown that the commitment for older and more experienced workers increases with high levels of autonomy, while the opposite is true for younger and less experienced workers. When workers experience greater control at the point of production, they express greater organizational commitment. Finally, being appointed to a certain position regardless of being a full-time faculty or a newly hired, has shown to increase productivity and strengthen organizational commitment. Human Resource Practices also influence an organizational characteristics called decentralization. Five Factor Model of Personality also has a bearing on the Constructs of Organizational Commitment, each factor to the three constructs: Affective, Normative, and Continuance. Agreeableness was found to be the importance personality variable in predicting relationships. Attachment style also has shown that it influences workplace behavior and attitude regarding leadership. And finally, relationship commitment was also measured to the future time orientation of couples and relationship commitment also has a bearing on age. Furthermore, commitment to friendships and families plays a part in predicting relationship commitment.

Perhaps the highlight from all the variables are the perceptions of workers differing in age in its relation to organizational commitment, there seems to be a disparity in views that takes effect on the organizational commitment. The dominant findings suggest that organizational commitment plays a vital role in the workplace and influences a myriad of variables that are yet to be covered. While most of the studies suggest that Organizational Commitment is a predictor of a plethora of variables, what most of the researches lack are the predictors that concerns and may influence Organizational Commitment in an organization or a workplace. The study regarding the Big Five Factor of Personality, specifically the variable Agreeableness plays a big part in relationship commitment because of its predictive power. Even commitment to friends and relationships affects relationship commitment and even the future time orientation of an individual to their relationship. And attachment style has a strong influence on a person's relationship

commitment. In addition, attachment style plays a role in workplace behavior and leadership roles. These variables namely: Agreeableness, Attachment style, and Relationship commitment happens to have a link to one another like Agreeableness to relationship commitment, attachment and relationship commitment, which can also be significant factors to consider in the workplace setting. The mere fact that there is an overlapping among the three variables: agreeableness, attachment style, and relationship commitment; the relationship of the three will have an important bearing on organizational commitment because the aim of the study is to see if the three variables can predict organizational commitment, so the relationship of each predictor to organizational commitment is important.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study was a Correlational quantitative research design which tackled numerous numerical data in gathering a great number of respondents.

Participants

A sample of 250 call center agents, who are working in a Call Center Agency: FIS Global Solutions in Magallanes and Startek Call Center Agency in Ortigas-Mandaluyong City. The researcher has also gathered samples from former call center agents who quit their job as call center agents. Participants were chosen by the use of purposive sampling which is directed to call center agents only or with the experience of working in a call center agency. The researcher searched for participants who fitted the criteria: Target Age is 18-50, roughly half would be male and half would be female for a total of 250 respondents, a year of experience was considered to be enough. This sampling technique was based on the population and the purpose of the study.

Research Instruments

The data needed for the study was gathered through demographic questionnaire and four scales measuring the chosen variables.

For Agreeableness, the researcher will use HEXACO Personality Inventory Revised (HEXACO-PI-R) (Ashton & Lee, 2009) and the HEXACO-60 a 60-item questionnaire in Likert Scale format will be used; sample items would be, "I rarely hold a grudge, even against people who have badly wronged me." and "I feel reasonably satisfied with myself overall." And it has a high Cronbach Alphas ranging from (.76) to (.80) namely: Honesty-Humility (.76), Emotionality (.80), Extraversion (.80), Agreeableness (.77), Conscientiousness (.76), and Openness to Experience (.78).

For Attachment style, The Revised Experiences in Close Relationships scale (ECR-R) (Fraley, Waller, & Brennan, 2000) a 36-item measure in Likert Scale format of adult attachment style will be used; sample items would be, "I'm afraid that I will lose my partner's love." and "I often worry that my partner doesn't really love me." And the Coefficient Alphas for the variables:

Avoidance (.93) and Anxiety (.92).

For Relationship Commitment, The Commitment Scale (Rusbult, 1987) a 15-item in Likert Scale will be used; sample items would be, “I will do everything I can to make our relationship last for the rest of our lives.” and “I feel completely attached to my partner and our relationship.” And the Alphas ranged from (.91) to (.95) for Commitment Level, (.92) to (.95) for Satisfaction Level, (.82 to .88) for Quality of Alternatives, and (.82) to (.84) for Investment Size.

For Organizational Commitment, the Three Component Model (TCM) of Employee Commitment Survey (Meyer & Allen, 1991; 1997) a 32-Item in Likert Scale format will be used, the sample items would be, “I really feel as if this organization’s problems are my own.” and “I enjoy discussing my organization with people outside it.” And the Internal consistency estimates (alpha coefficients) obtained in studies that have employed these scales range from (.74) to (.89) for the Affective Commitment, (.69) to (.84) for the Continuance Commitment, and (.69) to (.79) for the Normative Commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1990, 1993; Meyer & Allen, 1984; Meyer, et al., 1989).

Procedures

In order to conduct the study and gather the necessary data, the researcher went through the following procedures:

First, the researcher contacted a person who works in the said call center agency. Through a personal contact, it made the distribution of the questionnaires smooth without any complications regarding the management of the said call center. Second, the researcher came to the said call center headquarters and did an ocular inspection of the people and the venue. Third, the researcher gave his contact the questionnaires for the distribution. Fourth, the researcher observed how it was distributed and also on how the respondents were informed of the instructions. Fifth, the participants were asked to answer the questionnaires without a given time frame. Sixth, after the participants have answered, the questionnaires were asked to be returned for collection. The distribution and gathering of questionnaires happened for three trips in a span of three weeks.

Data Analysis

The statistical procedure used was Inferential Statistics for it would be making predictions about a population from observations and analyses from a sample. The data gathered from the questionnaires was analyzed through the statistical method called multiple linear regression analysis. Multiple Linear Regression analysis provides the relationship between the predictive variables: agreeableness, attachment style, and relationship commitment to the criterion variable: organizational commitment. The researcher used the Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) software for windows v.20, as the statistical tool in analyzing the data that was gathered. The SPSS result showed the Grand Mean of the respondents regarding with each variable, the correlation of each independent variable to Organizational Commitment, the coefficients of each variable, the ANOVA of each model, the Model Summary, and even P-P Plot, and scatter plot. The basis for the degree of the variables of the respondents and their levels will be displayed on Tables A-D:

Table A: Data Evaluation Degree of Agreeableness

Responses	Range	Interpretation
Strongly agree	4.50-5.00	Very High
Moderately agree	3.50-4.49	High
Agree	2.49-3.49	Average
Moderately disagree	1.50-2.49	Low
Strongly disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low

Table B: Data Evaluation Degree of Attachment Style

Responses	Range	Interpretation
Strongly disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low
Slightly disagree	1.50-2.49	Moderately Low
Disagree	2.50-3.49	Low
Neutral	3.50-4.49	Average
Agree	4.50-5.49	High
Slightly Agree	5.50-6.49	Moderately High
Strongly Agree	6.50-7.00	Very High

Table C: Data Evaluation Degree of Relationship Commitment

Responses	Range	Interpretation
Do Not Agree At All	0.00-0.49	Very Low
	0.50-1.49	Moderately Low
	1.50-2.49	Slightly Low
	2.50-3.49	Low
Agree Somewhat	3.50-4.49	Average
	4.50-5.49	High
	5.50-6.49	Slightly High
	6.50-7.49	Moderately High
Agree Completely	7.50-8.00	Very High

Table D: Data Evaluation Degree of Organizational Commitment

Responses	Range	Interpretation
Strongly disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low
Slightly disagree	1.50-2.49	Moderately Low
Disagree	2.50-3.49	Low
Neutral	3.50-4.49	Average
Agree	4.50-5.49	High
Slightly Agree	5.50-6.49	Moderately High
Strongly Agree	6.50-7.00	Very High

RESULTS

Degree of Agreeableness, Attachment Style, Relationship Commitment, and Organizational Commitment of the Respondents

The table would show the degree of Agreeableness, Attachment Style, Relationship Commitment, and Organizational Commitment of the Respondents. Also included is the alpha coefficients of each variable.

Table E. Grand Mean, Interpretation, and Internal-Consistency Reliability Coefficients (alphas) for Agreeableness, Attachment Style (AS), Relationship Commitment (RC), and Organizational Commitment (OC).

Variables	Grand Mean	Interpretation	α
Agreeableness	3.23	Average	.69
AS	3.45	Low	.93
RC	5.54	Slightly High	.97
OC	4.31	Average	.92

N=250

By using Descriptive Statistics, four scores comprised the variables for this study were generated for the average showed that with regards to Agreeableness, Relationship Commitment, Attachment Style and Organizational Commitment. Agreeableness scores were obtained as a subscale of HEXACO questionnaire, out of 60 items, 10 items were covered by Agreeableness which was used for the study. Relationship Commitment subscales: psychological attachment, intent to persist, and long-term orientation scores were obtained by averaging the ratings. Attachment scales which has two subscales of Anxiety and Avoidance items were combined and was both averaged to obtain scores for each participant, with lower scores indicating decreased levels of the dimensions. TCM Employee Commitment Survey - Normative Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Organizational Commitment scores were obtained by averaging the participants' scores on the scale. Grand Mean, interpretation, and internal-consistency reliabilities for each scale are displayed in Table E.

Correlations of Agreeableness, Attachment Style, Relationship Commitment to Organizational Commitment

Table F shows the Pearson r of each independent variable to the dependent variable including their significance level and the sample size. Each independent variable's result would be discussed below.

Table F. Correlations

	Agreeableness	AS	RC
Pearson R of OC	.22	.06	.51
Significance	.000	.182	.000
N	250	250	250

Agreeableness and Organizational Commitment

The second hypothesis of the study, and one of the five questions that wants to be answered by the researcher, predicted that Agreeableness would be associated with Organizational Commitment. The result found about the Pearson Correlation between Agreeableness and Organizational Commitment ($r = .22$; $p < .01$) is significant and has a weak positive relationship. The Agreeableness questionnaire that was used has a Cronbach Alpha of ($\alpha = .92$) based from getting the reliability statistic of one of the predictor variable.

Attachment Style and Organizational Commitment

The third main prediction of the study was that Attachment Style would be associated with Organizational Commitment. The result about the Pearson correlation between Attachment Style and Organizational Commitment ($r = .06$; $p > .01$) is not significant and has no presumption against the null hypothesis. The Attachment Style questionnaire that was used has a Cronbach Alpha of ($\alpha = .93$) based from the reliability statistic as one of the predictor variable. Although the reliability was high, it did not yield a strong correlation with Organizational Commitment. However, if the correlation between Agreeableness and Attachment Style would be considered, the result would be ($r = -.18$; $p < .05$) and it is slightly significant and has weak negative relationship. Though weak, the idea that the being high in Agreeableness would indicate lesser degree of Avoidant and Anxious attachment styles.

Relationship Commitment and Organizational Commitment

The fourth main prediction of the study was that Relationship Commitment would be associated with Organizational Commitment. The result about the Pearson correlation between Relationship Commitment and Organizational Commitment ($r = .51$; $p < .001$) is significant and has a moderate positive relationship. The Relationship Commitment questionnaire that was used has a Cronbach Alpha of ($\alpha = .97$) based from the reliability statistic as one of the predictor variables. This has a very moderate reliability to measure the Relationship Commitment. Among all the predictive variables, Relationship Commitment yield the greatest positive relationship. The result has a Moderate Positive Relationship, within the range of .40 to .59, based on Evans' (1996) guide on the absolute value of "r". Which the result of the research got a correlation coefficient of .51. The implication of this result would be Relationship Commitment has moderate positive

relationship with Organizational Commitment. People in an organization can become as committed to an organization as much as they are committed to their spouses or significant other; since there is moderate and positive relationship, the greater the commitment to relationships the greater the commitment to organizations.

Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Organizational Commitment as Predictors of Organizational Commitment

The fifth main prediction of the study was that the prediction model: Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment would significantly predict Organizational Commitment. To further illustrate the prediction model, the Model Summary result would be included.

Table G. Model Summary

Coefficients

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig.	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	.51 ^a	.26	.26	.000	Agreeableness = .568	Agreeableness = .168	3.071	.002
2	.53 ^b	.28	.27	.000	AS = .094	AS = .165	3.033	.003
3	.55 ^c	.31	.30	.000	RC = .452	RC = .507	9.341	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship Commitment, Agreeableness

c. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship Commitment, Agreeableness, Attachment Style

d. Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment

Since the statistical procedure used is Multiple Linear Regression, the Adjusted R Square would be considered in interpreting the result of the predictive model. If the first model would be considered with only Relationship Commitment as the predictor, it would yield to a Pearson Coefficient of .51 the same in reference to the Correlation chart that was previously shown. By considering the Adjusted R Square of Regression Model 1: Relationship Commitment, with a result of .26, by converting it to percentage, the result would report that 26% of the total variability in Organizational Commitment is explained by Regression Model 1: Relationship Commitment as the predictor. By considering the Adjusted R Square of Regression Model 2: Relationship Commitment and Agreeableness, with a result of .27, by converting it to percentage, the result would report that 27% of the total variability in Organizational Commitment is explained by Regression Model 2: Relationship Commitment and Agreeableness. What the study was aiming to answer is “Do **agreeableness, attachment style, and relationship commitment** significantly predict **organizational commitment**?” By considering the Adjusted R Square of Regression Model 3: Relationship Commitment, Agreeableness, and Attachment Style, garnering a result of .30, by converting to percentage, the result would report that 30% of the total variability in Organizational

Commitment is explained by Regression Model 3: Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment as the predictors. Since there are no big discrepancies from the result of the R Square and Adjusted R Square, the R Square was not considered. Hence, the Independent Variables in the regression model are not redundant. Considering the Pearson R of Regression Model 3, a score of .55 would indicate that it has a moderate positive relationship and significantly predicts Organizational Commitment.

By looking at the Model 1, there is a significant effect of Relationship Commitment as the lone variable to Organizational Commitment ($F_{1,248} = 86.4, p < .005$). With Model 2, there is also a significant effect of Relationship Commitment and Agreeableness to Organizational Commitment ($F_{1,247} = 47.8, p < .005$). With Model 3, there is also a significant effect of Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment to Organizational Commitment ($F_{1,246} = 36.0, p < .005$). The null hypothesis is rejected (the models having no predictive power) for the F test result for each model: 86.4, 47.8, and 36.0 were greater than their corresponding critical value 6.73, 4.69, 3.86 respectively.

Using the predictive model: Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment, the result shows that Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment are all significant ($p < .01$). Each independent variable has a predictive ability for the dependent variable Organizational Commitment. The high t score ($t = 9.34$) of Relationship Commitment is worth noting as it was the consistent independent variable with moderate predictive power that keeps on appearing from the different tests that were made.

Focusing on the Unstandardized Coefficients B, the signs are all positive. Having for each variable: Agreeableness = .568, AS = .094, and RC = .452. The interpretation for the coefficient of Agreeableness would be: for a .568 increase in Agreeableness the model predicts Organizational Commitment will increase or decrease by .168 holding all other independent variables equal. For Attachment Style, a .094 increase in Attachment Style the model predicts Organizational Commitment will increase or decrease by .165 holding all other independent variables equal. Also for Relationship Commitment, a .452 increase in Relationship Commitment the model predicts Organizational Commitment will increase or decrease by .507 holding all other independent variables equal. This shows the sensitivity of the dependent variable to the changes of the independent variable. Considering the significance level, each variable possess a unique significant contribution to the prediction. Relationship Commitment delivers the greatest contribution to the outcome, followed by Agreeableness, and lastly Attachment Style.

Another useful piece of information to consider is the Part Correlations Coefficient. Each variable contributes to the total R Square of the Model. Looking at the result, Relationship Commitment delivers the greatest influence by how it predicts Organizational Commitment. Removing Relationship Commitment would drastically affect the predictive power of the model.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to determine if individuals commit to their organizations as they do to their partners in their personal relationships, and if Organizational Commitment is correlated to Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment. Using purposive sampling, a total of 250 respondents were gathered from call center agencies and former call center agents within Metro Manila. What the researcher has found was that Agreeableness has a significant weak correlation with Organizational Commitment; Relationship Commitment has a significant positive correlation to Organizational Commitment, and Attachment Style was not significant and not correlated; Relationship Commitment was the highest correlated and greatest significant predictor of Organizational Commitment. Overall, there was a moderate positive correlation between Relationship Commitment and Organizational Commitment; increase in Relationship Commitment were correlated with increases in rating of Organizational Commitment. In connection, using Multiple Linear Regression showed that, as a whole, Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment are significant in predicting Organizational Commitment. Considering the three independent variables as one unified model would account for 30% of the variability in predicting Organizational Commitment. Implication of the study suggest that an individual's commitment to personal relationships can be a predictor of an individual's commitment to an organization and in application may help employers in screening applicants preventing unwanted turnovers. Since Organizational Commitment is a significant predictor of turnovers (Dijk and Brown, 2003); the problem of the study was about turnovers of employees, if there would be predictors of Organizational Commitment, it will precede and address the turnovers of employees by considering an applicant's Relationship Commitment.

Regarding the study's limitations, it is important to keep in mind that the Multiple Linear Regression model: Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment accounts for only 30% of the variability of Organizational Commitment. The 70% was not covered by this research and recommends future research to be done that will cover other unknown variables that accounts for Organizational Commitment as a whole. Although the model has great predictive ability, it should be taken in moderation since it does not cover the full Organizational Commitment of an employee. Furthermore, Relationship Commitment's moderate correlation and predictive power does not mean it is an absolute, but only to be a factor to be considered in hiring an employee.

Findings

Result of bivariate analysis revealed that employees' agreeableness and relationship commitment significantly correlated with organizational commitment. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that variances in organizational commitment can be significantly explained by the employees' relationship commitment, attachment style, and relationship commitment. In addition, although attachment style isn't strongly significant predictor, it has an influence when

considered as a whole with agreeableness and relationship commitment. Relationship commitment alone can be a predictor of Organizational Commitment.

Conclusion

Present research used three variables such as Agreeableness, Attachment Style, and Relationship Commitment in predicting Organizational Commitment of Call Center employees. Previous research suggests that Organizational Commitment is a predictor of wide set of variables, but there were few studies done here in the Philippines regarding organizational commitment, one is the study of work-life programs and organizational commitment in addressing turnover intentions (Ramos, 2004). All in all, present research conclude that Attachment Style is not a predictor of Organizational Commitment, but has an influence when Agreeableness and Relationship Commitment were held as constant. Agreeableness on the other hand is a weak predictor of Organizational Commitment. Relationship Commitment show as the strongest predictor of Organizational Commitment among all the independent variables.

Recommendation

Turnover is one of the greatest challenges that faces every organization, especially those in industries that has no promotion and are on contractual basis. Standardized test regarding Organizational Commitment can be used to obtain more quantifiable data with a larger sample. The use of Organizational Commitment as cited is not commonly used here in the Philippines with regards to Industrial Psychology. Therefore, different setting such as Construction or in business can be a preferable setting for studying Organizational Commitment. Given that Agreeableness as weak positively correlated and Relationship Commitment as moderate positively correlated to Organizational Commitment, it is recommended that it can be used to screen applicants for being potentially hired and preventing future turnovers, but it will not be the basis of recruitment. Directions for future research would encourage to find the other 70% that accounts for Organizational Commitment as a whole, since the study only covered the 30% accounted for Organizational Commitment.

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APPENDIX

For Agreeableness Sample

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HEXACO-PI-R

(SELF REPORT FORM)

© Kibeom Lee, Ph.D., & Michael C. Ashton, Ph.D.

DIRECTIONS

On the following pages you will find a series of statements about you. Please read each statement and decide how much you agree or disagree with that statement. Then write your response in the space next to the statement using the following scale:

- 5 = strongly agree
- 4 = agree
- 3 = neutral (neither agree nor disagree)
- 2 = disagree
- 1 = strongly disagree

Please answer every statement, even if you are not completely sure of your response.

Please provide the following information about yourself.

Sex (circle): Female Male

Age: _____ years

1 = strongly disagree 2 = disagree 3 = neutral 4 = agree 5 = strongly agree

- 1 _____ I would be quite bored by a visit to an art gallery.
- 2 _____ I plan ahead and organize things, to avoid scrambling at the last minute.
- 3 _____ I rarely hold a grudge, even against people who have badly wronged me.
- 4 _____ I feel reasonably satisfied with myself overall.
- 5 _____ I would feel afraid if I had to travel in bad weather conditions.
- 6 _____ I wouldn't use flattery to get a raise or promotion at work, even if I thought it would succeed.
- 7 _____ I'm interested in learning about the history and politics of other countries.
- 8 _____ I often push myself very hard when trying to achieve a goal.
- 9 _____ People sometimes tell me that I am too critical of others.
- 10 _____ I rarely express my opinions in group meetings.
- 11 _____ I sometimes can't help worrying about little things.
- 12 _____ If I knew that I could never get caught, I would be willing to steal a million dollars.
- 13 _____ I would enjoy creating a work of art, such as a novel, a song, or a painting.
- 14 _____ When working on something, I don't pay much attention to small details.
- 15 _____ People sometimes tell me that I'm too stubborn.
- 16 _____ I prefer jobs that involve active social interaction to those that involve working alone.
- 17 _____ When I suffer from a painful experience, I need someone to make me feel comfortable.
- 18 _____ Having a lot of money is not especially important to me.
- 19 _____ I think that paying attention to radical ideas is a waste of time.
- 20 _____ I make decisions based on the feeling of the moment rather than on careful thought.
- 21 _____ People think of me as someone who has a quick temper.
- 22 _____ On most days, I feel cheerful and optimistic.
- 23 _____ I feel like crying when I see other people crying.
- 24 _____ I think that I am entitled to more respect than the average person is.
- 25 _____ If I had the opportunity, I would like to attend a classical music concert.
- 26 _____ When working, I sometimes have difficulties due to being disorganized.
- 27 _____ My attitude toward people who have treated me badly is "forgive and forget".
- 28 _____ I feel that I am an unpopular person.
- 29 _____ When it comes to physical danger, I am very fearful.
- 30 _____ If I want something from someone, I will laugh at that person's worst jokes.

Continued...

For Attachment Style Sample

Shiota, M.N., Keltner, D., & John, O. P. (2006). Positive emotion dispositions differentially associated with Big Five personality and attachment style. *The Journal of Positive Psychology, 1*, 61-71.

Although theorists have proposed the existence of multiple distinct varieties of positive emotion, dispositional positive affect is typically treated as a unidimensional variable in personality research. We present data elaborating conceptual and empirical differences among seven positive emotion dispositions in their relationships with two core personality constructs, the "Big Five" and adult attachment style. We found that the positive emotion dispositions were differentially associated with self- and peer-rated Extraversion, Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, Openness to Experience, and Neuroticism. We also found that different adult attachment styles were associated with different kinds of emotional rewards. Findings support the theoretical utility of differentiating among several dispositional positive emotion constructs in personality research.

Scale:

The statements below concern how you feel in emotionally intimate relationships. We are interested in how you *generally* experience relationships, not just in what is happening in a current relationship. Respond to each statement by circling a number to indicate how much you agree or disagree with the statement.

	QUESTION	1=Strongly Disagree.....	2	3	4	5	6	7=Strong Agree
1.	I'm afraid that I will lose my partner's love.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2.	I often worry that my partner will not want to stay with me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3.	I often worry that my partner doesn't really love me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4.	I worry that romantic partners won't care about me as much as I care about them.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5.	I often wish that my partner's feelings for me were as strong as my feelings for him or her.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6.	I worry a lot about my relationships.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7.	When my partner is out of sight, I worry that he or she might become interested in someone else.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8.	When I show my feelings for romantic partners, I'm afraid they will not feel the same about me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9.	I rarely worry about my partner leaving me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10.	My romantic partner makes me doubt myself.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11.	I do not often worry about being abandoned.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12.	I find that my partner(s) don't want to get as close as I would like.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13.	Sometimes romantic partners change their feelings about me for no apparent reason.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14.	My desire to be very close sometimes scares people away.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15.	I'm afraid that once a romantic partner gets to know me, he or she won't like who I really am.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16.	It makes me mad that I don't get the affection and support I need from my partner.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17.	I worry that I won't measure up to other people.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18.	My partner only seems to notice me when I'm angry.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19.	I prefer not to show a partner how I feel deep down.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20.	I feel comfortable sharing my private thoughts and feelings	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

For Relationship Commitment Sample

***Note that this scale can be modified for either marital relationships or dating relationships by substituting relationship for marriage.**

Reference:

- This is an elaborated version of the commitment measure cited in:
Rusbult, C. E., Martz, J. M., & Agnew, C. R. (1998). The investment model scale: Measuring commitment level, satisfaction level, quality of alternatives, and investment size. *Personal Relationships, 5*, 357–391.
- This 15-item measure was used in:
Rusbult, C. E., Kumashiro, M., Kubacka, K. E., & Finkel, E. J. (2009). “The part of me that you bring out”: Ideal similarity and the Michelangelo phenomenon. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 96*, 61-82.

My Goals for the Future of our Relationship

Instructions:

To what extent does each of the following statements describe your feelings regarding your relationship? Please use the following scale to record an answer for each statement listed below.

Response Scale:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Do Not Agree			Agree			Agree		
At All			Somewhat			Completely		

Response

- 1) I will do everything I can to make our relationship last for the rest of our lives.
- 2) I feel completely attached to my partner and our relationship.
- 3) I often talk to my partner about what things will be like when we are very old.
- 4) I feel really awful when things are not going well in our relationship.
- 5) I am completely committed to maintaining our relationship.
- 6) I frequently imagine life with my partner in the distant future.
- 7) When I make plans about future events in life, I carefully consider the impact of my decisions on our relationship.
- 8) I spend a lot of time thinking about the future of our relationship.
- 9) I feel really terrible when things are not going well for my partner.
- 10) I want our relationship to last forever.
- 11) There is no chance at all that I would ever become romantically involved with another person.
- 12) I am oriented toward the long-term future of our relationship (for example, I imagine life with my partner decades from now).
- 13) My partner is more important to me than anyone else in life – more important than my parents, friends, etc.
- 14) I intend to do everything humanly possible to make our relationship persist.
- 15) If our relationship were ever to end, I would feel that my life was destroyed.

APPENDIX A

Commitment Scales

Instructions

Listed below is a series of statements that represent feelings that individuals might have about the company or organization for which they work. With respect to your own feelings about the particular organization for which you are now working, please indicate the degree of your agreement or disagreement with each statement by circling a number from 1 to 7 using the scale below.

- 1 = strongly disagree
- 2 = disagree
- 3 = slightly disagree
- 4 = undecided
- 5 = slightly agree
- 6 = agree
- 7 = strongly agree

Original Version (Allen & Meyer, 1990)

Affective Commitment Scale

- 1) I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.
- 2) I enjoy discussing my organization with people outside it.
- 3) I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.
- 4) I think that I could easily become as attached to another organization as I am to this one. (R)
- 5) I do not feel like 'part of the family' at my organization. (R)
- 6) I do not feel 'emotionally attached' to this organization. (R)
- 7) This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.
- 8) I do not feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization. (R)

SPSS Outputs

Regression

[DataSet2] C:\Users\user\Desktop\AG_AT_RC_OC - CorrelationLatest.sav

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Organizational_Commitment	74.0720	20.42153	250
Agreeableness	32.2760	6.03136	250
Attachment_Style	124.2480	35.72534	250
Relationship_Commitment	70.4200	22.91813	250

Correlations

		Organizational _Commitment	Agreeableness	Attachment_S tyle
Pearson Correlation	Organizational_Commitment	1.000	.220	.058
	Agreeableness	.220	1.000	-.183
	Attachment_Style	.058	-.183	1.000
	Relationship_Commitment	.509	.163	-.152
Sig. (1-tailed)	Organizational_Commitment	.	.000	.182
	Agreeableness	.000	.	.002
	Attachment_Style	.182	.002	.
	Relationship_Commitment	.000	.005	.008
N	Organizational_Commitment	250	250	250
	Agreeableness	250	250	250
	Attachment_Style	250	250	250
	Relationship_Commitment	250	250	250

Correlations

		Relationship_Commitment
Pearson Correlation	Organizational_Commitment	.509
	Agreeableness	.163
	Attachment_Style	-.152
	Relationship_Commitment	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Organizational_Commitment	.000
	Agreeableness	.005
	Attachment_Style	.008
	Relationship_Commitment	.
N	Organizational_Commitment	250
	Agreeableness	250
	Attachment_Style	250
	Relationship_Commitment	250

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Relationship_Commitment	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= .100).
2	Agreeableness	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= .100).
3	Attachment_Style	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= .100).

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational_Commitment

Model Summary^d

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.509 ^a	.260	.257	17.60800
2	.528 ^b	.279	.273	17.41225
3	.552 ^c	.305	.296	17.13032

a. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment, Agreeableness

c. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment, Agreeableness, Attachment_Style

d. Dependent Variable: Organizational_Commitment

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26952.407	1	26952.407	86.932	.000 ^b
	Residual	76890.297	248	310.042		
	Total	103842.704	249			
2	Regression	28955.681	2	14477.841	47.752	.000 ^c
	Residual	74887.023	247	303.186		
	Total	103842.704	249			
3	Regression	31654.489	3	10551.496	35.957	.000 ^d
	Residual	72188.215	246	293.448		
	Total	103842.704	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational_Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment

c. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment, Agreeableness

d. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment, Agreeableness, Attachment_Style

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	42.104	3.605		11.679
	Relationship_Commitment	.454	.049	.509	9.324
2	(Constant)	28.156	6.492		4.337
	Relationship_Commitment	.434	.049	.487	8.885
	Agreeableness	.477	.185	.141	2.570
3	(Constant)	12.175	8.281		1.470
	Relationship_Commitment	.452	.048	.507	9.341
	Agreeableness	.568	.185	.168	3.071
	Attachment_Style	.094	.031	.165	3.033

Coefficients^a

Model		Sig.	Correlations		
			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	(Constant)	.000			
	Relationship_Commitment	.000	.509	.509	.509
2	(Constant)	.000			
	Relationship_Commitment	.000	.509	.492	.480
	Agreeableness	.011	.220	.161	.139
3	(Constant)	.143			
	Relationship_Commitment	.000	.509	.512	.497
	Agreeableness	.002	.220	.192	.163
	Attachment_Style	.003	.058	.190	.161

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational_Commitment

Excluded Variables^a

Model		Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
						Tolerance
1	Agreeableness	.141 ^b	2.570	.011	.161	.974
	Attachment_Style	.138 ^b	2.525	.012	.159	.977
2	Attachment_Style	.165 ^c	3.033	.003	.190	.951

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational_Commitment

b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment

c. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Relationship_Commitment, Agreeableness

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	32.0416	90.9346	74.0720	11.27504	250
Residual	-52.69377	76.56324	.00000	17.02682	250
Std. Predicted Value	-3.728	1.496	.000	1.000	250
Std. Residual	-3.076	4.469	.000	.994	250

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational_Commitment

Graph 1.

The graph shows that the distribution of the scores were normal since the dots are near in the line of best fit. There is a deviation from the normality along the 0.2 to .04 of the plot, since most of those who answered the questionnaires usually chose high scores. The respondents opt for high scores in Organizational Commitment as it may affect their status in the company they work for. That is why there is a deviation from the normality at the lower end. However, taken the P-P Plot in general, the plotted points mostly follow the straight line, having greater inclination to normality.

Graph 2.

As what was shown in Graph 1 following the normality, the points in Graph 2 have the same dispersion line over the predicted range. From above, we can see no clear relationship between the residuals and the predicted values which is consistent with the assumption of linearity. The points regress to the line of best fit.